

Fluid inclusion isotopic signals from Variscan quartz veins using a new CRDS method

Akbar Aydin Oglu Huseynov, H.J.L van der Lubbe, S.J.A. Verdegaal – Warmerdam, O. Postma
Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam
a.huseynov@vu.nl

Fluid inclusions of quartz veins are essential for determining the pathways of fluids flow in the subsurface. In this study, we provide a new method for analysing the isotopic composition of fluid inclusion water via Cavity Ring-Down Spectroscopy (CRDS). The CRDS is connected to a mechanical crusher to release fluid inclusion water from the mineral it is contained in, at a temperature of around 120°C. The water vapour from the pulverised sample is introduced into a wet background that has a consistent composition and concentration of oxygen and hydrogen isotopes. The Earth Science Stable Isotope Laboratory at the Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam (VU) has designed a temperature-controlled evaporation system that ensures a consistently stable background.

This newly designed configuration offers accurate measurements of the combined oxygen and hydrogen isotope compositions from quartz grains. In this work, we examined quartz veins from Germany and Portugal that are associated with the Variscan orogeny. The isotopes results are consistent with the current Global Meteoric Water Line and indicate the meteoric impact on this fold-and-thrust belt. The silicon and oxygen isotopic characteristics of quartz crystals, together with microthermometric studies, provide evidence of the hydrothermal system undergoing cooling at various phases of the Variscan orogeny, in conjunction with the isotopic data obtained from fluid inclusions. This technique enables direct measurement of isotopic compositions of fluid inclusions, offering a quicker and more efficient alternative to current approaches. Moreover, it may be used to a wide range of minerals and geological environments.

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